

A Comparative Study of 2% Lidocaine Plus 0.5% Ropivacaine Versus 2% Lidocaine Plus 0.5% Bupivacaine for Peribulbar Anesthesia in Cataract Surgeries

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Abstract

Introduction: The goals of safe and effective anesthesia for intraocular surgery is to obtain good analgesia and anesthesia without complications. Peribulbar anesthesia has been the anesthesia of choice for cataract surgery and is routinely performed with a mixture of local anesthetics, most common combination being bupivacaine and lidocaine. The aminoamide, Ropivacaine, a derivative of mepivacaine, was introduced in 1996 as the safer alternative to bupivacaine.

Hence, we compared the efficacy and complications of ropivacaine and bupivacaine, both in combination with lidocaine and hyaluronidase for peribulbar anesthesia by two-point injection technique for cataract surgery.

Materials and Methods: In this study, 60 consenting patients posted for cataract surgery under peribulbar anesthesia with two-point injection technique were included. They were randomly categorized into two groups of 30 patients each. One group received ropivacaine with lidocaine plus hyaluronidase and the other group received bupivacaine with lidocaine plus hyaluronidase.

The efficacy was compared in terms of akinesia and analgesia achieved by each of these agents both intraoperatively and postoperatively. Results were analyzed using paired t test, ANOVA, and chi-square test.

Results: Based on our observations regarding onset of action, duration of anesthesia, early recovery of motor blockade and intraocular pressure changes, ropivacaine scored better than bupivacaine. There were no differences in effects on mean arterial pressure and ECG rhythm changes and even though bupivacaine decreased heart rate from baseline value, bradycardia did not occur in both groups.

Conclusion: Ropivacaine is a better agent than bupivacaine for peribulbar anesthesia due to its faster onset and shorter duration with less effects on intraocular pressure. However, cardiovascular toxicity does not occur with either ropivacaine or bupivacaine when used in peribulbar anesthesia for cataract surgery.

Keywords: Ropivacaine; Bupivacaine; Peribulbar anesthesia; Intraocular pressure.

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Introduction

Regional anesthesia has been used ever since Percy first proposed the use of cocaine as a topical anesthetic in 1856. [1] The goals of safe and effective anesthesia for intraocular surgery are to obtain good analgesia and akinesia without complications.

Peribulbar anesthesia has been the anesthesia of choice for cataract surgery and is routinely performed with a mixture of local anesthetics, most commonly bupivacaine and lidocaine.[2]

After the introduction of bupivacaine, it became apparent that accidental overdose was often fatal due to its cardiotoxic effect and responded poorly to conventional resuscitation methods.[1]

The aminoamide, Ropivacaine, a derivative of mepivacaine, was introduced in 1996 as the safer alternative to bupivacaine. It possesses properties similar to those of bupivacaine but is less neurotoxic and cardiotoxic.[3]

In 1999, Huha et al did a study in patients scheduled for cataract surgery under peribulbar anesthesia and concluded that ropivacaine group had more rapid and complete akinesia when compared to bupivacaine group.[4]

Hence, we compared the effects of ropivacaine and bupivacaine, each combined with lidocaine and hyaluronidase for peribulbar anesthesia by two-point injection technique, in patients posted for cataract surgery.

Materials and Methods

After approval of institutional ethics committee, 60 consenting patients fulfilling the inclusion criteria were considered for our study. A pre-anesthetic checkup was done for all patients which included a detailed history, general physical and systemic examination. Ophthalmologic examination was done by the ophthalmologist including intraocular pressure measurement. Basic investigations including a baseline ECG were done. Patients were kept nil per oral overnight.

Ophthalmology resident who was not connected with our study loaded the study drugs and the operating surgeon performed peribulbar anesthesia.

Intraoperative and postoperative assessment was

done by anesthesia resident who was blinded to study drugs.

Patients were randomized into two groups of 30 each using computer generated random sequence table.

GROUP A: Receiving 0.5% ropivacaine plus 2% lidocaine plus 30U/ml of Hyaluronidase

GROUP B: Receiving 0.5% bupivacaine plus 2% lidocaine plus 30U/ml of Hyaluronidase

In the operating room, two-point peribulbar anesthesia was administered with 7ml mixture of local anesthetics at the superonasal and inferolateral quadrants in all cases with the eye in primary position of gaze.

Table 1: Akinesia Scoring System

Akinesia of extraocular muscles, including the levator muscle	
0	0–1mm movement in one or two main directions or 0–4mm movement in the levator muscle.
1	2mm movement in any main direction or 1mm movement in more than two directions or > 4mm movement in the levator muscle
2	>2mm movement in any main direction or 2mm movement in two or more main directions
Akinesia of orbicular muscle	
0	Complete akinesia
1	Partial movement in either or both eyelid margins
2	Pronounced movement in either or both eyelid margins

- Akinesia was scored as described by sarvela et al (Table 1) at 2mins interval for the first 10mins, then every 15mins till 1hr and every half an hour for next 2hrs.
- Time of onset was recorded when globe akinesia score is 0
- Sensory anesthesia assessed as present or absent and intraocular pressure were measured at the recorded time of onset.
- Time to recovery was noted when akinesia score of 1 is obtained.
- Heart rate and mean arterial pressure were recorded at 2mins interval for the first 10mins, thereafter every 15mins till 1hr and every half an hour for next 2hrs.
- Intraocular pressure was measured at the time of onset.
- Rhythm disturbances in ECG were recorded as present or absent.

Collected data was analyzed by t test, ANOVA (analysis of variance) and Chi-square test.

Results

Eyelid Akinesia Score

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Table 2: Eyelid Akinesia Score- Group A

Group A Time(mins)	Eyelid akinesia grade		
	0	1	2
2	76.7	10.0	13.3
4	96.7	3.3	0
6	100.0	0	0
8	100.0	0	0
10	100.0	0	0
15	100.0	0	0
30	100.0	0	0
45	16.7	76.7	6.7
60	0	16.7	83.3
120	0	0	100.0
180	0	0	100.0

values are in percentage of patients

In group A, at 2 min 23(76.7%), at 4 min 29(96.7%) and at 6 min 30(100%) patients had eyelid akinesia score of grades 0. At 2 min, only 4(13.3%) patients had grade 2 and by 4 min no

patients were having eyelid akinesia score of grades 2. At 45 min, grade 1 score was present in 23(76.7%) patients and by 60 min, 25(83.3%) patients had eyelid akinesia score of grades 2.

Table 3: Eyelid Akinesia score- Group B

Group B Time(mins)	Eyelid akinesia grade		
	0	1	2
2	0	0	100.0
4	3.3	0	96.7
6	6.7	3.3	90.0
8	16.7	83.3	0
10	100.0	0	0
15	100.0	0	0
30	100.0	0	0
45	100.0	0	0
60	90.0	10	0
120	0	83.3	16.7
180	0	0	100.0

values are in percentage of patients

Whereas, in group B, at 6 min, still 27(90%) patients had grade 2 and at 10 min, 30(100%) had grade 0

eyelid akinesia score. At 60 min, only 3(10%) patients had grade 1 and 120 min, still 25(83.3%) patients had grade 1 score.

Global Akinesia Score

Table 4: Global Akinesia Score- Group A

Group A Time(mins)	Global akinesia grade		
	0	1	2
2	66.7	16.7	16.7
4	96.7	3.3	0
6	100.0	0	0
8	100.0	0	0
10	100.0	0	0
15	100.0	0	0
30	100.0	0	0
45	40.0	60.0	0
60	3.3	36.7	60.0
120	3.3	3.3	93.3
180	3.3	0	96.7

values are in percentage of patients

In group A, 20(66.7%) patients had global akinesia score of grades 0 at 2 min, 29(96.7%) had grade 1 at 4min and 30(100%) patients, grade 2 at 6 min. At

4min, only 1(3.3%) had grade 1 and at 45min,

18(60%) patients had grade 1 score. By 60 min, only 1(3.3%) patient had grade 0 score of global akinesia.

Table 5: Global Akinesia score- Group B

Group B Time(mins)	Global akinesia grade		
	0	1	2
2	0	0	100.0
4	0	0	100.0
6	3.3	6.7	90.0
8	16.7	60.0	23.3
10	76.7	23.3	0
15	100.0	0	0
30	100.0	0	0
45	100.0	0	0
60	93.3	6.7	0
120	0	93.3	6.7
180	0	3.3	96.7

values are in percentage of patients

In contrast to group A, in group B, at 4 min, still all (100%) patients had global akinesia score of grades 2. At 8 min, only 5(16.7%) had grade 0. At 60 min, still 28(93.3%) patients had grade 0 of global

akinesia score, and only at 120 min, 28(93.3%) patients attained grade 1 score.

Onset

Table 6: Onset of Akinesia

Group	Time(mins)			P value
	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	
A	2	6	2.73	0.000 HS
B	6	15	10.77	

HS- highly significant

The time required to attain a global akinesia score of grade 0 was as follows;

For group A, the minimum time required was 2 min

and maximum of 6 min with average 2.77 min for group B, the minimum time was 6 min and maximum of 15 min with average 10.77 min.

The difference between two groups was statistically significant with a p value of 0.00.

Figure 1: Onset of Akinesia

Mean Heart Rate

Table 7: Mean Heart Rate

Time(mins)	Group A	Group B
0	74.53 ±5.917	79.07 ±9.048
2	74.70 ±6.143	78.87 ±8.464
4	74.90 ±6.002	80.40 ±9.103
6	76.20 ±6.651	80.80 ±8.923
8	76.47 ±7.099	82.27 ±8.878
10	76.20 ±7.739	81.00 ±8.449
15	76.53 ±7.995	80.13 ±8.788
30	77.80 ±8.540	81.33 ±8.841
45	77.87 ±8.253	81.67 ±9.038
60	76.80±8.130	82.20±8.588
120	76.30±7.544	83.33±8.409
180	75.93±7.817	83.13±8.165

values are in mean heart rate(bpm) ± standard deviation

There was no significant decrease in the heart rate in group A.

However, group B showed a significant decrease in

the heart rate from baseline values at 8, 60, 120 and 180 mins. However, bradycardia was not seen in either group A or group B.

Mean Arterial Pressure

Table 8: Mean Arterial Pressure

Time(mins)	Group A	Group B
0	96.87±3.702	95.73±5.866
2	97.00±4.807	95.93±5.813
4	98.20±4.649	96.40±4.910
6	98.80±5.423	97.27±5.078
8	98.40±5.157	96.87±5.138
10	98.07±4.683	96.80±4.254
15	98.53±4.424	97.80±3.537
30	98.73±4.085	97.60±3.654
45	98.40±3.379	97.00±2.959
60	98.40±4.561	97.53±3.267
120	98.40±3.729	97.47±3.014
180	98.87±3.848	97.60±3.420

values are in mean arterial pressure(mm Hg) ± standard deviation

There was no significant change in mean arterial pressure from the baseline value in both the group at any time during the observation.

Intraocular Pressure

Table 9: Intraocular Pressure

Group		Mean IOP (mm Hg)	p value
A	Before	12.77±1.223	0.165 NS
	After	13.00±1.365	
B	Before	13.33±1.583	0.000 HS
	After	21.63±2.539	

values are in mean ± standard deviation
NS- not significant, HS- highly significant

There was no significant change in intraocular pressure after peribulbar anesthesia in group A, whereas in group B, highly significant increase in intraocular pressure was observed when compared to preoperative value.

Electrocardiographic Changes

Both in group A and group B, ECG rhythm changes were absent in all patients during the course of the study.

Recovery

Table 10: Duration of Anesthesia

Group	Mean duration(mins)	p value
A	51±7.474	0.000 HS
B	116±15.222	

values are in mean ± standard deviation
HS- highly significant

While comparing the time to recovery, the observations were as follows:

In group A, the minimum time to recovery was 45 min and a maximum of 60 min. on an average, the

patients in group A recovered from peribulbar block in 51 min. In contrast to group A, the patients in group B required an average of 116 min to recover from block. This difference was statistically highly significant with a p value 0.00.

Figure 2: Duration of Anesthesia

Discussion

Anesthesia plays a vital role in ophthalmic surgeries. Most cataract surgeries are done under peribulbar anesthesia.

The aim of anesthesia in cataract surgery is to provide adequate analgesia and akinesia and it should be safe without any untoward side effects. The peribulbar technique has gained much popularity when compared to retrobulbar technique. Peribulbar anesthesia has an added advantage of causing hypotony of the globe due to the loss of extraocular muscle tone.

The most recently introduced local anesthetic, ropivacaine, possesses properties similar to those of bupivacaine but is less neurotoxic and cardiotoxic. Ropivacaine has not yet been compared with the

commonly used anesthetic mixtures for ophthalmologic surgery.

Peribulbar anesthesia with two-point injection technique was in frequent use in our institution. Bupivacaine alone might seem more appropriate, however, the lidocaine-bupivacaine mixture is currently used in our institution as combining lidocaine's faster onset of action and long postoperative pain relief of bupivacaine are more beneficial. So, we compared the effects of two local anesthetics, bupivacaine and ropivacaine, each administered with lidocaine, on the quality of the block obtained after peribulbar anesthesia. A visual analog scale could not be used to assess pain in this patient population because of their poor vision. The two groups in our study were comparable with respect to age, gender, and weight

distribution.

Onset and Recovery

Our study showed that in ropivacaine group, 20 patients (66.7%) had a global akinesia score of grade 0 at 2 min and all had a score of grade 0 by 6 min, as compared to the study by Huha et al⁴, who reported more rapid development of akinesia with ropivacaine than bupivacaine at 2 min, this difference may be because they used a higher concentration of ropivacaine (1%).

As per our observations, the average time of onset was 2.77 min in ropivacaine group and 10.77 min in bupivacaine group. This is in accordance with a study done by Nociti et al⁵, who reported that percentage of patients showing successful block was higher in ropivacaine group at 1 and 5 min intervals after the injection than bupivacaine group and at 10 min, all patients in both groups had successful peribulbar anesthesia. Thus, showing that ropivacaine has a faster onset of action than bupivacaine.

In contrast to our observations, Gioia et al [6] did a study for vitreoretinal surgeries under peribulbar anesthesia and reported that surgical block was achieved after 8±5 min in the lidocaine-bupivacaine group as compared to 10±5 min in the ropivacaine group (without lidocaine) and concluded that ropivacaine has an onset similar to that of lidocaine-bupivacaine mixture. Although a higher concentration of ropivacaine (0.75%) was used in this study, the similar onset may be due to the confounding factor lidocaine which was added only with bupivacaine but not with ropivacaine. This is further strengthened by Perello et al [7] who showed a slower onset of akinesia using ropivacaine alone while comparing with ropivacaine plus lidocaine and bupivacaine plus lidocaine.

In our study, the time to recovery from peribulbar anesthesia was 51 min in ropivacaine group and 116 min in bupivacaine group, whereas Huha et al⁵ showed no difference in duration of action between ropivacaine and bupivacaine. However, Simpson et al⁸ used ropivacaine for regional anesthesia and acute pain management and observed that ropivacaine has lower incidence of motor block than bupivacaine which is an advantage for postoperative and labour pain.

This shorter duration of action and early motor recovery from ropivacaine may be particularly useful in cataract surgeries which are most commonly performed as outpatient surgeries, thus allowing early and safe discharge of the patient from hospital and also prolonged paralysis leaves the eye vulnerable to drying and trauma.

Cardiovascular Effects

In a study by Luchetti et al [9], cardiac arrhythmias

were more frequent in bupivacaine- mepivacaine group than ropivacaine group. Minor cardiac arrhythmias (ectopic beats) were observed in 22 patients (2.2%) with ropivacaine and 80 patients (8%) with bupivacaine-mepivacaine.

Scott et al [10] studied effects of intravenous infusion of ropivacaine and bupivacaine both at a rate of 10 mg/min, although both groups showed evidence of depression of conductivity and contractility, these appeared at lower dosage and lower plasma concentrations with bupivacaine than ropivacaine.

Knudsen et al [11] also conducted similar study by intravenous infusion of ropivacaine and bupivacaine both at a rate of 10 mg/min and recorded that bupivacaine increased QRS width during sinus rhythm compared to placebo and ropivacaine. Bupivacaine reduced both left ventricular systolic and diastolic function, while ropivacaine reduced only systolic function.

Although literature suggests better cardiac profile for ropivacaine than bupivacaine, majority of those studies are either through direct intravenous infusion of drugs or conducted in animals which cannot be extrapolated for regional anesthesia and in humans, respectively.

While comparing the cardiovascular toxicity in our study there was no significant change in heart rate from baseline values in ropivacaine group whereas bupivacaine group showed a significant decrease in heart rate from baseline values at 8, 60, 120 and 180 mins. But this decrease was only relative and bradycardia was not observed in any patient included in our study.

The changes in mean arterial pressure from baseline value were not significant in both the groups and there were no ECG rhythm changes in any patient during the course of our study.

This is supported by McLure et al [12] who found no difference in the frequency of adverse cardiac effects between ropivacaine group and the lidocaine and bupivacaine group. Fujita et al [13], in an animal study, reported that lidocaine attenuates any conduction abnormality induced by bupivacaine. However, in this study no direct comparisons with ropivacaine or bupivacaine were made, nor are there any reports in humans of this interesting effect.

Thus, we concluded that both ropivacaine and bupivacaine does not produce cardiovascular toxicity when administered for peribulbar anesthesia.

However, irrespective of the wider safety margin compared with other local anaesthetics, there are reports of toxic reactions with ropivacaine and care must still be taken with the administration of any highly concentrated local anaesthetic. [14,15]

Intraocular Pressure

The study done by Nocitti et al [5] showed that mean IOP (mm Hg) was 13.4 ± 3.2 in ropivacaine group when compared to 20.8 ± 4.7 in bupivacaine group, this effect is probably explained by vasoconstriction produced by ropivacaine leading to smaller intraocular blood volume.

We observed a significant increase of mean IOP (mm Hg) in bupivacaine group from 13.33 to 21.63 whereas in ropivacaine group it increased from

12.77 to 13.00 after peribulbar anesthesia.

Ozcan et al [16] observed that bupivacaine-lidocaine combination increased IOP from 15.1 ± 2.5 to 17.8 ± 2.5 after the peribulbar anesthesia, whereas ropivacaine decreased IOP from 15.8 ± 2.3 to 13.5 ± 2.3 . This increase in IOP by bupivacaine-lidocaine mixture may be due to vasodilation caused by lidocaine. But this confounding factor was absent in our study, as lidocaine was used in both groups. This effect of lidocaine may have resulted in absence of any fall in IOP with ropivacaine in our study. Even though there was rise in IOP with ropivacaine, it was significantly lower when compared to that of bupivacaine group.

In contrast to our study, Olmez et al [17] observed, while comparing ropivacaine alone with lidocaine with adrenaline, that although the IOP level of the ropivacaine group at 10min was significantly lower with respect to baseline level, there were no significant differences in the IOP levels between the two groups. This further explains that ropivacaine has vasoconstrictive property, as adrenaline causes vasoconstriction leading to similarity between the two groups.

This is also supported by Goveia et al [18], who observed that the mean IOP level in bupivacaine group before the blockade was 13.28 ± 2.35 mmHg, while in the ropivacaine group it was 13.1 ± 2.26 mmHg. Five minutes after the peribulbar anesthesia, the IOP in bupivacaine group increased to 15.62 ± 4.31 mm Hg and it reduced to 12.98 ± 2.71 mm Hg in ropivacaine group. They attributed this difference to vasoconstrictive effect of ropivacaine.

Limitations of our Study

1. In our study, sensory anesthesia was recorded only at the onset of motor blockade, thus we cannot say whether there was adequate sensory anesthesia present before motor block and if present, the onset of sensory anesthesia.
2. Similarly, we didn't look for sensory anesthesia while recording the time for recovery and thus we cannot comment on postoperative analgesia.
3. Complications of peribulbar anesthesia were not recorded.

Scope for further Studies

1. Intraoperative monitoring with echocardiography can be used to compare cardiovascular toxicity of bupivacaine and ropivacaine.
2. Effect of premedication on intraocular pressure changes with ropivacaine or bupivacaine can be studied.

Conclusion

This study showed that the combination of ropivacaine with lidocaine results in earlier onset, shorter duration, and lesser intraocular pressure changes than bupivacaine with lidocaine and cardiovascular toxicity is not seen with either ropivacaine or bupivacaine when used in peribulbar anesthesia for cataract surgery. Hence, we concluded that ropivacaine is a superior alternative to bupivacaine for peribulbar anesthesia in patients posted for cataract surgeries due to its better efficacy without any cardiovascular toxicity.

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